

Building Museum Identity Online: Two Decades of Progress

Nadezhda Povroznik

Perm State University 614990, Perm, Russia

povroznik.ng@gmail.com

With the opening of the Internet for public access, museums began to create their first websites, develop and upload content. At this key moment, a new and unique identity began to take shape, along with the formation of an understanding of the significance of museums' presence in the online environment, awareness of their importance and special role in this digital space. The ambition of museums in the virtual environment at this time reflected their vision to lead in the development of digital resources as well as to contribute to innovation and the political sphere. Therefore, it is important to consider the formation of the digital identity of museums from the moment of the creation of the first Internet resources.

An analysis of the issues of digital identity formation by museums is closely related to the study of the history of virtual museums, and the current study is based on the results of the project "Digital History of Virtual Museums", carried out at the Center for Contemporary and Digital History (University of Luxembourg) [1].

Turning to the consideration of the concept of "digital identity", the term is used in computer science and informatics and refers to the unique information used by computer systems to verify an external agent for access, with the digital identity appearing as "set of attributes related to an entity" [2].

There are also a variety of identities in the world such as gender, cultural, national, scientific and other identities; however, in this study, digital identity refers to museums in the online environment as having a presence on the Internet. In this sense, "digital identity" can also be part of the research field of identity studies, which is developing theoretically and in relation to the features of the digital age [3].

Identity can be inherent both to individuals and to organizations striving for the effective achievement of their own goals. The case of museum information resources is particularly insightful since the formation of the digital identity of a museum might be considered as the transformation of a simple museum website into a virtual museum [4]. The shaping of digital identity is a simultaneous process with the understanding and awareness of new functions that the museum obtains in the digital age.

Taking into account the accumulated experience in developing museum information resources, the formation of digital identity should be a conscious process for ensuring effectiveness in the implementation of new museum functions. Therefore, the topic of the digital identity of museums is important for research because museums are able to ultimately become more proficient by developing the most suitable resources to survive in an age of digital abundance.

Identity is not constructed instantly. Some elements of a museum's identity may appear obvious and others have a hidden potential, revealed gradually. Web archives [5] are the crucial sources for reconstructing the processes of building and developing the digital identity by

museums in the Internet environment. Snapshots of museum websites provide important information about the content and appearance of the particular resources at a certain point in time. Web-archives are able to reveal the functions museums performed online and the audiences they were oriented to, etc. Thus, the archived snapshots and meta-information about websites allow us to reconstruct the digital identity of the museum and observe its evolution.

The following components of digital identity, from this perspective, are key points in the reconstruction of the museum's digital identity.

Firstly, an important trigger for digital identity is the specific name given by the museum to the created website. At present the titles of museum websites are often associated with the name of a real museum; however many resource names in the mid-1990s emphasized their specific role, being called Museum Online, Museum Explorer, Digital Museum, Virtual Museum, etc.

Secondly, it is an expression of the museum image through the information on the main page of the website that gives a basic idea of the key components of the resource. To determine digital identity, the visual means located on the main page of the websites is crucial. These pictures represent significant figures that the museum uses to demonstrate priorities in its activities. So, for example, the first snapshot of the Metropolitan Museum's website contains an image of the entrance to the museum building, which hosts the exhibitions and symbolizes an invitation to visit the museum [6]. Other museums also had been posting images of remarkable buildings associated with particular museums. However, then these images were gradually displaced by the pictures emphasizing the museums as places of storage and representation of cultural heritage. Images of noteworthy objects from the museums' collections have been appearing on the main page of the websites, which demonstrates a shift in the priorities of activities online.

Thirdly, website functionality is an important characteristic of digital identity. First of all, various digital initiatives are significant because they allow visitors to use a museum's resources remotely. Also, created content inevitably targets a specific category of users, therefore understanding the audience of online visitors plays an important role in the reconstruction of digital identity.

The digital identity of museums has changed significantly over their web history. From understanding the function of a website as a means of advertising a visit to a real museum, museums have progressed to understanding the significance of diversity of functions to solve various issues, attract virtual visitors before, during, after and instead of visiting a real museum, to engage different types of communities, including virtual ones.

References

- [1] Digital History of Virtual Museums, <http://virtualmuseumhistory.com>
- [2] General Terms. ISO/IEC 24760-1:2019(E). IT-security and Privacy - A framework for identity management. Part 1. Terminology and Concepts. 2019. P. 1.
- [3] Davis J.L. (2016) Identity Theory in a Digital Age. In: Stets J.E., Serpe R.T. (Eds.) New Directions in Identity Theory and Research. Pp. 137-164.

[4] Povroznik N. (2018) Virtual Museums and Cultural Heritage: Challenges and Solutions. Proceedings of the Digital Humanities in the Nordic Countries 3rd Conference, Helsinki, Finland, March 7-9, 2018.

[5] Internet Archive. Wayback Machine, <https://archive.org>

[6] Metropolitan Museum. Wayback Machine. Snapshot of the Main Page on
11 November 1996,
<https://web.archive.org/web/19961111003737/http://www.metmuseum.org>